

Iridium(III) Chloride catalysed Oxidation of some Alcohols by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

M. P. SINGH*, P. K. TANDON, R. M. SINGH and ALKA MEHROTRA

Chemical Laboratories, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

Manuscript received 24 July 1989, revised 15 December 1989, accepted 6 February 1990

The oxidation of methanol, ethanol, propanol-1 and butanol-1 by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) using iridium(III) chloride as a homogeneous catalyst reveals first order kinetics at low concentrations, thereafter the rate of the reaction becomes independent with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III) and hydroxide ions each at their higher concentrations. The reaction follows direct proportionality with respect to $[\text{IrCl}_6]$, and increase in the ionic strength of the medium effects the reaction rate in a positive manner. The probable pathway for the oxidation of the above alcohols and the rate law have been derived. The thermodynamic parameters have also been calculated.

TRANSITION metal ions have widely been used as homogeneous catalysts in the oxidation of organic compounds in acidic or alkaline medium. Use of osmium tetroxide as homogeneous catalyst¹ was limited in the alkaline medium only because it is toxic in acidic medium and hence it was replaced by ruthenium² and iridium³ compounds. Mechanistic steps in iridium(III) chloride catalysis were first explained by Tandon and Krishna³ in the oxidation of acetone. After this only little work has been done. This prompted us to study the oxidation of methanol, ethanol, propanol-1 and butanol-1 by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) using iridium(III) chloride as a homogeneous catalyst.

Experimental

The solutions of methanol, ethanol, propanol-1 and butanol-1 (AnalaR and Riedel) were prepared in double-distilled water. The solution of iridium(III) chloride (Johnson Matthey) was prepared in hydrochloric acid. The final strengths of the catalyst and acid were 3.34×10^{-3} and $2.74 \times 10^{-3} M$ respectively. All other chemicals were either AnalaR or chemically pure grade. Temperature of the reaction was kept constant with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The progress of the reaction was measured at different intervals of time by estimating the amount of hexacyanoferrate(II) produced by titrating it against a standard solution of ceric sulphate using ferroin as a redox indicator. In all the kinetic runs alcohol was present in excess.

Results and Discussion

Iridium(III) chloride catalysed oxidation of methanol, ethanol, propanol-1 and butanol-1 was studied at constant ionic strength of the medium where the uncatalysed reaction was negligible.

The reaction rate (Table 1) shows direct proportionality with respect to hexacyanoferrate(III) at its low concentrations and tends to become zero order with respect to the oxidant at its higher concentrations. The data (Tables 2 and 3) indicate that the rate of the reaction follows first order kinetics with respect to the substrate and hydroxide ions at their low concentrations while it tends to become zero order with respect to both at their higher concentrations. A steady increase in the values (Table 4) indicates first order kinetics with respect to iridium(III) chloride concentration even up to its manifold variation. This nature is confirmed from the constancy in the first order rate constants k_1 values (where $k_1 = dc/dt/[\text{IrCl}_6]$). Table 5 shows that there is a gradual increase in the rate values with the increasing ionic strength of the medium showing positive effect of the ionic strength of the medium on the reaction rate.

The stoichiometry of the reaction was studied by taking hexacyanoferrate(III) in large excess as compared to alcohols in different ratios and the observations were made for a long period. The estimation of unconsumed hexacyanoferrate(III) by usual method showed that four moles of the oxidant are required for the complete oxidation of one mole of the substrate according to equation (1),

The corresponding acids were identified with the help of paper chromatography and spot-test methods⁴. The final oxidation products in case of methanol, ethanol, propanol-1 and butanol-1 were found to be formic, acetic, propionic and butanoic acid respectively. The rate of reaction in different substrates was found follow the order : butanol-1 > propanol-1 > ethanol > methanol, showing that the rate of oxidation increases with the addition of

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]$ ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

	$[K_3Fe(CN)_6] \times 10^3 M$										
	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	7.00	8.00	9.00	10.00	
(A) $[NaOH]=0.60 M$, $[Methanol]=0.55 M$, $[IrCl_3]=3.342 \times 10^{-5} M$, $\mu=1.50 M$	2.50	4.20	5.40	6.40	7.20	8.10	9.00	9.70	10.40	—	—
(B) $[NaOH]=0.60 M$, $[Ethanol]=0.55 M$, $[IrCl_3]=3.342 \times 10^{-5} M$, $\mu=1.50 M$	3.00	5.00	6.50	7.30	8.50	9.60	—	12.00	—	14.00	—
(C) $[NaOH]=0.15 M$, $[Propanol-1]=0.10 M$, $[IrCl_3]=5.03 \times 10^{-5} M$, $\mu=1.00 M$	1.55	2.40	3.15	3.75	4.40	5.10	5.60	6.00	—	—	—
(D) $[NaOH]=0.20 M$, $[Butanol-1]=0.10 M$, $[IrCl_3]=3.342 \times 10^{-5} M$, $\mu=1.00 M$	2.00	2.63	3.38	4.25	5.38	5.63	6.15	6.25	—	—	—

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [SUBSTRATES] ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

(A) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]=2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH]=0.50 M$, $[IrCl_3]=6.684 \times 10^{-5} M$, $\mu=1.50 M$	$[Methanol] (M)$		0.10	0.25	0.75	1.00	3.00	4.00	6.00	9.00			
	$-dc/dt$		1.00	1.75	2.25	2.50	3.25	3.50	4.00	4.75			
	$\times 10^5 (M \text{ min}^{-1})$												
(B) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]=2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH]=0.55 M$, $[IrCl_3]=3.342 \times 10^{-5} M$, $\mu=1.50 M$	$[Ethanol] (M)$		0.10	0.20	0.75	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	7.00	9.00
	$-dc/dt$		1.00	1.50	2.15	2.50	2.70	2.90	3.10	3.30	3.55	3.75	4.20
	$\times 10^5 (M \text{ min}^{-1})$												
(C) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]=2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH]=0.15 M$, $[IrCl_3]=3.342 \times 10^{-5} M$, $\mu=1.00 M$	$[Propanol-1] (M)$		0.25	0.50	1.50	2.50	3.00	3.50	4.00	4.50	5.50		
	$-dc/dt$		0.80	1.80	6.00	9.80	11.20	13.00	14.10	16.00	18.00		
	$\times 10^5 (M \text{ min}^{-1})$												
(D) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]=2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH]=0.15 M$, $[IrCl_3]=5.013 \times 10^{-5} M$, $\mu=1.00 M$	$[Butanol-1] (M)$		0.10	0.30	0.60	1.00	1.40	1.80	2.20	2.60			
	$-dc/dt$		1.00	2.20	3.90	5.70	7.30	8.70	9.80	10.80			
	$(\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1})$												

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF $[OH^-]$ ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

(A) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]=2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Methanol]=0.50 M$, $[IrCl_3]=5.013 \times 10^{-5} M$, $\mu=1.50 M$	$[NaOH] (\times 10 M)$		0.10	0.25	0.50	2.00	3.00	4.00	6.00	7.00	9.00
	$-dc/dt$		0.75	1.35	1.65	2.35	2.95	3.25	4.10	4.50	5.25
	$(\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1})$										
(B) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]=2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Ethanol]=0.50 M$, $[IrCl_3]=5.013 \times 10^{-5} M$, $\mu=1.50 M$	$[NaOH] (\times 10 M)$		0.25	0.50	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	7.00
	$-dc/dt$		0.75	1.10	1.40	2.10	2.70	3.20	3.70	4.20	4.70
	$(\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1})$										
(C) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]=2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Propanol-1]=0.10 M$, $[IrCl_3]=3.342 \times 10^{-5} M$, $\mu=1.00 M$	$[NaOH] (\times 10 M)$		0.25	0.50	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	
	$-dc/dt$		0.47	0.90	1.83	3.50	4.80	5.01	5.05	5.12	
	$(\times 10^5 M \text{ min}^{-1})$										
(D) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]=2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Butanol-1]=0.10 M$, $[IrCl_3]=3.342 \times 10^{-5} M$, $\mu=1.00 M$	$[NaOH] (\times 10 M)$		0.20	0.40	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	
	$-dc/dt$		0.80	1.60	4.00	7.00	10.00	12.00	14.00	15.00	
	$(\times 10^5 M, \text{ min}^{-1})$										

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF $[IrCl_3]$ ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

(A) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]=2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH]=0.40 M$, $[Methanol]=0.40 M$, $\mu=1.50 M$	$k_1 = -dc/dt/[IrCl_3]$										
(B) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]=2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH]=0.40 M$, $[Ethanol]=0.40 M$, $\mu=1.50 M$	$(i) -dc/dt$										
(C) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]=2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH]=0.20 M$, $[Propanol-1]=0.10 M$, $\mu=1.00 M$	$(\times 10^4 M \text{ min}^{-1})$										
(D) $[K_3Fe(CN)_6]=2.00 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[NaOH]=0.15 M$, $[Butanol-1]=0.10 M$, $\mu=1.00 M$	$(ii) k_1 (\text{min}^{-1})$										
	$[IrCl_3] (\times 10^5 M)$	1.671	3.342	5.013	6.684	8.355	10.026	11.697	13.368		
(A) (i)		1.30	—	4.00	5.30	6.60	7.90	9.20	10.50		
(A) (ii)		0.78	—	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.78		
(B) (i)		1.20	2.30	3.50	4.60	5.70	7.00	8.10	9.20		
(B) (ii)		0.72	0.69	0.70	0.69	0.68	0.70	0.70	0.70		
(C) (i)		1.50	2.90	4.25	5.06	7.00	8.50	9.70	11.20		
(C) (ii)		0.89	0.86	0.85	0.76	0.84	0.85	0.83	0.84		
(D) (i)		1.70	3.40	5.20	7.00	8.70	10.50	—	14.00		
(D) (ii)		1.01	1.02	1.03	1.04	1.04	1.04	—	1.04		

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF IONIC STRENGTH OF THE MEDIUM ON REACTION RATE AT 35°

[K₂Fe(CN)₆]=2.00 × 10⁻³ M, [IrCl₃]=3.342 × 10⁻⁵ M
 (A) [Methanol]=0.50 M [NaOH]=5.0 × 10⁻³ M
 (B) [Ethanol]=0.50 M [NaOH]=5.0 × 10⁻³ M
 (C) [Propanol-1]=0.10 M [NaOH]=2.0 × 10⁻² M
 (D) [Butanol-1]=0.10 M [NaOH]=2.0 × 10⁻² M
 -dc/dt (× 10⁵ M min⁻¹)

[KCl] × 10 ³ M	(A)	(B)	(C)	(D)
0.10	—	—	1.25	1.00
0.15	1.75	1.50	—	—
0.20	—	—	1.45	1.25
0.30	2.00	1.75	1.65	1.50
0.40	—	—	1.85	1.85
0.45	2.15	2.00	—	—
0.50	—	—	2.05	2.00
0.60	2.40	2.10	2.25	2.30
0.70	—	—	2.50	2.50
0.75	2.60	2.60	—	—
0.90	2.80	2.85	—	—
1.05	3.10	3.05	—	—
1.20	3.30	3.30	—	—

methyl group in molecule. This sequence is also confirmed from the thermodynamic parameters, i.e. ΔE, ΔS and ΔF (Table 6) calculated from the data obtained at four different temperatures viz. 30, 35, 40 and 45° (±0.1°). It is clear from the values of energy of activation and entropy that the formation of activated complex is easy in alcohols having large structures. These values also confirm that similar mechanism is operative in the oxidation of all the aforesaid alcohols.

It has been reported⁶ that IrCl₃ in hydrochloric acid medium gives IrCl₆³⁻ species. It has also been reported⁶ that Ir³⁺ and Ir⁴⁺ are the stable oxidation states of iridium and there is no evidence of formation of Ir²⁺ species in the literature. Further, the aquation of IrCl₆³⁻ gives IrCl₅(H₂O)²⁻, IrCl₄(H₂O)₂⁻ and IrCl₃(H₂O)₃ species⁷⁻⁹ as shown by the equation,

Since no retarding effect of Cl⁻ ions observed hence the hydrated species cannot be the reactive species of IrCl₃. Hence, [IrCl₆]³⁻ has been considered as the only reactive species of IrCl₃ in the present study.

Thus on the basis of the above results the probable pathway for the oxidation of aforesaid alcohols might be described as follows.

where, [Fey]=[Fe(CN)₆³⁻]

According to the above scheme alkoxide ion with IrCl₆³⁻ forms complex C₁ which again combines with ferricyanide to give another complex C₂^{10,11}. Formation of such type of complexes under similar conditions has been reported by Tandon and Krishna in the oxidation of propan-2-one⁸. The complex C₂ then slowly decomposes into the intermediate products and Ir³⁺ species. This Ir³⁺ species quickly gets oxidised by taking more of ferricyanide ions into IrCl₅(H₂O)²⁻ species. The first oxidation products are further oxidised to give the final oxidation products, and IrCl₅(H₂O)²⁻ species by taking Cl⁻ ion gives back the Ir³⁺ species. The formation of the complexes C₁ and C₂ is confirmed by the plots of 1/rate vs 1/[substrate], 1/[NaOH] and 1/[catalyst]. Straight lines with positive intercepts confirm the formation of the complexes¹². Nature of the plot obtained in the substrate variation, i.e. direct proportionality of the reaction rate at lower concentrations of the substrate which becomes independent with respect to the substrate at its higher concentration itself, confirms the complex formation between the substrate and the catalyst. Spectroscopic evidence for the formation of above complexes could not be provided because of the very short life of the complexes and due to the interference produced by the substrate and other reactants. The positive effect of the increase in ionic strength of the medium on the reaction rate itself supports that the reaction is taking place between the similarly charged ions. Moreover, the results obtained can be explained very accurately by the above mechanism.

From the above mechanism the concentrations C₁, C₂ and catalyst can be given as

$$[\text{C}_1] = K_1[\text{S}^-][\text{Ir}] \quad (2)$$

$$[\text{C}_2] = K_3[\text{C}_1][\text{Fey}] \quad (3)$$

$$\text{and } [\text{Cat.}] = \frac{[\text{C}_1]}{K_1 K_2 [\text{S}][\text{OH}^-]} \quad (4)$$

The total concentration of the catalyst can be given as

$$[\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{C}_1] + \frac{[\text{C}_1]}{K_1 K_2 [\text{S}][\text{OH}^-]} + [\text{C}_2] \quad (5)$$

At steady state condition, with the help of equations (2-5) the rate of disappearance of ferricyanide can be given as

$$V_1 = -\frac{d[\text{Fey}]}{dt} = \frac{k K_1 K_2 K_3 [\text{S}][\text{OH}^-][\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}[\text{Fey}]}{1 + K_1 K_2 [\text{S}][\text{OH}^-] \{1 + K_3 [\text{Fey}]\}} \quad (6)$$

This equation clearly explains the nature shown by ferricyanide, substrate, hydroxide ions and iridium(III) chloride.

On the basis of the experimental results at low concentrations of [S], [OH⁻] and [Fey], one might assume the inequality, $1 \gg K_1 K_2 [S][OH^-]$ and $1 \gg K_3 [Fey]$ and the equation (6) reduces to

$$-\frac{d[Fey]}{dt} = k K_1 K_2 K_3 [S][OH^-][Ir^{III}]_T [Fey] \quad (7)$$

Equation (7) well explains the direct proportionality of the reaction rate with respect to the substrate, hydroxide ions, ferricyanide and iridium(III) at their low concentrations.

At higher concentrations of substrate, hydroxide ion and ferricyanide the reverse inequality, $1 \ll K_1 K_2 [S][OH^-]$ and $1 \ll K_3 [Fey]$ will hold good and equation (6) becomes

$$-\frac{d[Fey]}{dt} = k [Ir^{III}] \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) clearly explains the first order kinetics with respect to iridium(III) chloride concentrations even up to its manifold variation. This equation also explains that at higher concentrations the rate of the reaction will become independent with respect to the substrate, hydroxide ions and ferricyanide concentrations.

The validity of the rate-law (6) might be seen by rewriting it as

$$\frac{1}{V_1} = \frac{1}{k [Ir^{III}]_T} + \frac{1}{k K_3 [Fey] [Ir^{III}]_T} + \frac{1}{k K_1 K_2 K_3 [S][OH^-][Fey][Ir^{III}]_T} \quad (9)$$

The plots of $1/\text{rate}$ vs $1/[Fey]$, $1/[S]$ and $1/[OH^-]$ (Figs. 1–3) give straight lines with positive intercepts at Y-axes. From the intercept of the plots of $1/V_1$ vs $1/[Fey]$, the k values were calculated.

Fig. 1. (A) [NaOH]=0.60 M, [Methanol]=0.55 M, [IrCl₃]=3.342 × 10⁻⁵ M, μ=1.50 M; (B) [NaOH]=0.60 M, [Ethanol]=0.55 M, [IrCl₃]=3.342 × 10⁻⁵ M, μ=1.50 M; (C) [NaOH]=0.15 M, [Propanol-1]=0.10 M, [IrCl₃]=5.013 × 10⁻⁵ M, μ=1.00 M; (D) [NaOH]=0.15 M, [Butanol-1]=0.10 M, [IrCl₃]=3.342 × 10⁻⁵ M, μ=1.00 M.

Fig. 2. (A) [K₃Fe(CN)₆]=2.00 × 10⁻³ M, [NaOH]=0.50 M, [IrCl₃]=6.684 × 10⁻⁵ M, μ=1.50 M; (B) [K₃Fe(CN)₆]=2.00 × 10⁻³ M, [NaOH]=0.55 M, [IrCl₃]=3.342 × 10⁻⁵ M, μ=1.50 M; (C) [K₃Fe(CN)₆]=2.00 × 10⁻³ M, [NaOH]=0.15 M, [IrCl₃]=3.342 × 10⁻⁵ M, μ=1.00 M; (D) [K₃Fe(CN)₆]=2.00 × 10⁻³ M, [NaOH]=0.15 M, [IrCl₃]=5.013 × 10⁻⁵ M, μ=1.00 M.

Fig. 3. (A) [K₃Fe(CN)₆]=2.00 × 10⁻³ M, [Methanol]=0.50 M, [IrCl₃]=5.013 × 10⁻⁵ M, μ=1.50 M; (B) [K₃Fe(CN)₆]=2.00 × 10⁻³ M, [Ethanol]=0.40 M, [IrCl₃]=5.013 × 10⁻⁵ M, μ=1.50 M; (C) [K₃Fe(CN)₆]=2.00 × 10⁻³ M, [Propanol-1]=0.10 M, [IrCl₃]=2.507 × 10⁻⁵ M, μ=1.00 M; (D) [K₃Fe(CN)₆]=2.00 × 10⁻³ M, [Butanol-1]=0.10 M, [IrCl₃]=2.507 × 10⁻⁵ M, μ=1.00 M.

Similarly from the slopes of the plots of $1/V_1$ vs $1/[S]$ and $1/[OH^-]$, the $K_1 K_2$ values were calculated (Table 6). Straight lines with positive intercepts and

TABLE 6—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AND CALCULATED RATE CONSTANTS FOR HEXACYANOFERRATE(III) OXIDATION OF ALCOHOLS AT 35°

Compd.	ΔE^\ddagger × 10 ⁻³ J mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger × 10 ⁻⁴ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔF^\ddagger × 10 ⁻³ J mol ⁻¹
Methanol	85.71	-6.22	19.22
Ethanol	48.44	-18.36	56.57
Propanol-1	44.84	-19.66	60.58
Butanol-1	40.49	-20.91	64.44

(Table 6 contd.)

	From plot Rate vs [S] $kK_1K_2K_3$ ($\times 10^3$)	From intercept		From slope	
		$1/[Fe^{2+}]$	$1/[S]$ and $1/[OH^-]$ ($\times 10^2$)	$1/[OH^-]$	$1/[S]$
	k	K_3 ($\times 10^2$)	K_1K_2	K_1K_2	
Methanol	35.00	1.00	1.07 1.07	33.00	33.00
Ethanol	76.00	1.50	1.25 1.27	40.00	40.00
Propanol-1	400.00	0.80	2.00 2.00	251.00	270.00
Butanol-1	800	4.00	3.75 3.70	46.80	50.60

*At low concentrations of [S] and $[OH^-]$.

practically constant values of k , K_1K_2 and K_3 from different graphs confirm the validity of the rate law (6) and hence the proposed mechanism.

References

1. V. N. SINGH, A. C. GROVER, B. B. L. SAXENA and M. P. SINGH, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1969, **47**, 1051.
2. P. K. TANDON, MANIBALA, H. S. SINGH and B. KRISHNA, *Z. Phys. Chem., (Leipzig)*, 1984, **265**, 609.
3. MANIBALA, H. S. SINGH, B. KRISHNA and P. K. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 434.
4. F. FRIGL, "Spot Tests In Organic Chemistry", Elsevier, New York.
5. J. C. CHANG and C. S. GARNER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 209.
6. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry" Wiley Eastern Ltd., New Delhi.
7. A. J. P. DOMINGOS, A. M. T. S. DOMINGOS and J. M. P. CABRAL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31** 2563.
8. V. I. KRAVTSOV and G. M. PETROVA, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem. (Engl. Transl.)*, 1964, **9**, 552.
9. A. POUlsen and C. S. GARNER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 2032.
10. D. K. SINGH, D. Phil. Thesis, Allahabad University, 1981.
11. H. C. GUPTA, Ph. D. Thesis, Meerut University, 1981.
12. MICHALIS and M. L. MENTEN, *Biochem. J.*, 1933, **49**, 333.